

Performance of Chuan Mi 2 at the Sichuan RRI in regional tests, and in adaptive research trials. Luzhou, Sichuan, China, 1983-88.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Chuan Mi 2	Local check
<i>Rice Research Institute trial</i>		
1983	7.2	6.9
1984	8.3	8.0
1985	7.2	6.4
Mean	7.6	7.1
<i>Regional test in Sichuan Province</i>		
1986	7.7	7.4
1987	7.1	6.6
Mean	7.4	7.0
<i>Adaptive research trial</i>		
1988	7.4	6.9

Chuan Mi 2 was screened in the greenhouse for resistance to important diseases of the area: it is resistant to blast. □

TTB14-1 fits ahu (autumn) season in double-cropped areas of Assam

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TTB14-1, a semidwarf variety derived from CRM13-3241/Kalinga 2 at RARS, Titabar, is suitable for ahu (autumn) season in rainfed high to medium-altitude lands in Assam. Optimum sowing and transplanting dates are Mar/Apr and Apr/May, respectively.

In transplanting experiments 1984-88, average TTB14-1 yield was 3.4 t/ha. This variety has been gaining

Table 1. Characteristics of TTB14-1. Assam, India, 1984-88.

Plant height	95 cm
Panicle length	23.0 cm
Grain type	Medium
1000-grain weight	22.0 g
Grain length	7.89 mm
Grain length/width	2.94
Kernel length	5.75 mm
Kernel length/width	2.36
Kernel color	White

popularity among farmers because of its high yield potential and because its 110-120 d growth duration enables

planting in double-cropped areas.

General characteristics and yield are given in Tables 1 and 2. □

Table 2. Yield and duration of TTB14-1 at different locations. Assam, India, 1984-88.

Year	Location	Season ^a	TTB14-1		Check		
			Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)
1984	Titabar	Ahu	3.1	118	Ch63	1.7	113
1986	FTS, Gelapukhuri	Ahu	2.5	117	Takuguni	1.4	117
1987	Titabar	Sali	3.0	110	Ratna	2.9	118
1988	Titabar	Ahu	4.7	120	Ratna	4.0	128
1988	FTS, Gelapukhuri	Ahu	4.0	110	Takuguni	1.9	114
		Mean	3.4	115		2.4	118

^aAhu = fall, sali = winter.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of boiling water treatment on germination and growth of *Sesbania rostrata*

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Dormancy in *S. rostrata* seeds can be broken by boiling water treatment. We studied the effect of length of boiling water treatment on germination and growth in a pot experiment Jan-Mar 1989.

Well-developed seeds (25/set) were treated with 98 °C water for 0 to 75 s at 15-s intervals, with 3 replications. Seeds were sown in pots filled with Vertisol and grown for 65 d with regular watering. Plants were uprooted and root and shoot portions separated and dried in a hot air oven at 65-70 °C to a uniform moisture content.

Treatment with boiling water significantly improved germination (see table). Duration of treatment did not significantly affect dry matter production. □

Influence of boiling water (98 °C) seed treatment on germination and dry matter production of *Sesbania rostrata* at Dharwad, India.

Treatment	Plants/pot (no.)	Germination (%)	Shoot dry weight (g/pot)	Root dry weight (g/pot)	Total dry weight (g/pot)
Control (no treatment)	1.0	4	1.47	0.30	1.77
Treatment with 98 °C water for					
15 s	15.3	62	4.93	0.83	5.76
30 s	17.3	70	6.50	1.10	7.60
45 s	19.0	76	5.75	0.90	6.65
60 s	19.0	76	5.50	0.96	6.46
75 s	19.3	78	5.98	0.81	6.79
SE±	0.4		0.75	0.12	0.85
LSD (P=0.5)	1.4		2.36	0.36	2.69